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Prevalence of Geohelminths Parasites Identified among Primary School Children in Anambra North Senatorial District, Southeast Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Over the years geohelminths infection has pose a significant risk to public health, the rate of co-infection of this helminthiasis with other infectious diseases has not been critically looked into, therefore this research aimed at determining the prevalence of Geohelminths parasitic infection, among primary school children in Anambra North. This was conducted from July 2024 – June 2025, in seven randomly selected primary schools across Anambra North, A total of 1029 faecal and blood samples were collected from children aged 3-15years and 700 water samples were also collected to access the environmental contamination, both samples were analysed for Geohelminths infection using flotation and sedimentation techniques. The Geohelminths eggs isolated were subjected to Polymerase Chain Reaction for confirmatory test before inoculation. Data obtained were analysed using SPSS version 20.0 with a significance level ($P \geq 0.05$). Out of 1029 samples, 1010 samples were examined, 175 pupils harboured at least one parasite species 175(17.32%). *Ascaris lumbricoid* 47(26.86%) is the most prevalence, while *Ancylostoma duodenale* record the least prevalence rate 28(16.00%). This study contributes to knowledge by showing that inhabitants of different villages in seven L.G.A, in Anambra North have high prevalence of Geohelminths *Ascaris lumbricoid*.

Keywords: *Ancylostoma duodenale*, Environmental Contamination, Geohelminths Infection and Sedimentation Techniques

1. INTRODUCTION

The understanding of infectious diseases has been deeply influenced by the fathers of microbiology, Robert Koch and Louis Pasteur, who independently demonstrated the relationship between the microbial world and disease. (Winn *et al.*, 2016). Their work and rationale led directly to the identification and characterization of the etiological agents of the world's major infectious diseases. Further research, noted that the causal relationship between microbial agents and disease can be less straightforward than previous research work described by Koch and Pasteur, with a variety of pathogenic factors and host bodies affecting the incident and outcome of disease, particularly in cases of opportunistic infections associated with a compromised host immune system. (Ayinmode *et al.*, 2010). The term “geohelminths” and “geohelminthiasis” is usually meant several species of nematodes and associated diseases that are ecologically related although taxonomically and phylogenetically heterogeneous. The name comes from the Greek. γῆ “soil, terrain” ἔλμινξ -ινθος “worm”, thus indicating that these worms are strictly depending

from soil environment for a critical developmental stage of their life cycles. Geohelminths, also known as soil transmitted helminths (STHs), belong to several orders of nematodes that are responsible of specifically human diseases as well as of zoonotic infections. The nematodes specific to humans are mostly responsible for intestinal diseases at their adult stage while most of the zoonotic species exert their pathogenic effects through larval aberrant migrations that can be cutaneous, visceral or cerebral. Geohelminthiasis represent the most widespread parasitic diseases in the world, accounting for over 1.5 billion infections (around 24% of the entire world's human population), being probably more frequent than any other infectious disease, including those from bacteria and viruses. Many mammalian-parasitic nematodes infect only one or a limited number of host species, but zoonotic transmissions and coinfections may also occur.

2. Study Area

The study was carried out in Anambra North Senatorial zones, one of the three senatorial zones in Anambra State of Nigeria. It covers an area approximately 4416 km² and lies at Latitude of 6°20'N and longitude 7°00'E. Anambra North Senatorial District is made up of 7 local governments. They are as follows: Anambra East (Umuleri, Igbariam, Nando, Nsugbe, Eziagulu-Otu, Mkpunando, Enugwu-Aguleri, Umuoba-Anam and Otuocha), Anambra West (Nzam, Ezi-Anam, Ifite-Anam, Olumbanasa, Orom-Etiti, Umueze-Anam and Umuenwelum-Anam), Ayamelum (Anaku, Omor, Igbakwu, Umumbo, Umueje, Umuerum, Ifite-Ogwari and Omasi), Ogbaru (Atani, Akili-Ozizo, Amiyi, Mputu, Obe agwo, Ohita, Odekpe, Ogbakuba, Ochuche, Umuuodu, Ossomala, Ogwu-Anocha, Umunamkwo, Umuzu, Okpoko and Ogwu-ikpere), Onitsha North, Onitsha South and Oyi Local Government Area (Nteje, Awkuzu, Ogbunike, Nkwere-Ezunaka and Umunya). The senatorial district has abundant natural resources; Occupations in the Area were predominantly fishing, farming (mainly known for rice farming), Hunting and business. Anambra North senatorial district soil is predominantly shaly formation and geographically of forest zone, *Onyenweife and Nwozor (2025)*.

Figure 1. Map of study Area showing the 7 local governments Area with sample sites.

Source: *Onyenweife and Nwozor (2025)*

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Ethical Consideration

Institutional approval was obtained from Anambra State Ministry of Health Awka. Also, informed verbal consent was obtained from all the participants' guidance. The participants were informed about the research; its objectives and participation were voluntary. Participants were assured that every data collected would be handled confidentially and would be used for research purposes. (Appendix 1)

3.2 The Study Population and sample size

The population comprises primary school pupils between the ages 3-15years in the seven LGA which made up Anambra North Senatorial District. Twenty primary schools were randomly selected for the study. Three schools from each LGA were selected based on stratified random sampling while two schools were selected in Onitsha South LGA for having the least number of schools. A total of one thousand and twenty-nine pupils representing 5% were selected for the study between July, 2024 to June, 2025.

Table 3.1 Name of LGA, number of School, Population of pupils and sample size used for the study.

S/NO	LGA	NO. OF SCHOOLS	POPULATION OF PUPILS	POPULATION USED
1	AYAMELUM	50	3,180	159
2	ANAMBRA WEST	47	2,812	142
3	ANAMBRA EAST	50	2,755	138
4	OYI	42	2,814	141
5	ONITSHA SOUTH	29	1,429	100
6	ONITSHA NORTH	39	2653	133
7	OGBARU	59	4,318	216
	TOTAL	316	19,961	1029

(Anambra Primary Education Board, data baseline 2024)

3.3 Sample size calculation

The sample size was calculated based on Cochran's 1977 formula and the 16.2% STH prevalence from informal settlements reported in Kisumu (Odiere *et al.*, 2011). The choice of Kisumu as reference was since the study was done in public primary school children from informal settings with similar aspects.

$$n = \frac{z^2(p)(1-p)}{(d)^2} \qquad n = \frac{1.962(0.162)(1-0.162)}{(0.05)^2}$$

Where

n= sample size

p= prevalence of infection in the region (%)

d= absolute precision required

z=1.96 at 95% confidence level

Therefore, sample size = 1029 pupils.

The study factored 5% of the total samples (19,961) to cater for those pupils who might not return samples or might be absent from school on the day of sample collection

3.4 Sample collection

A total of 1029 faecal, 1029 blood and 700 water samples were collected between July, 2024 to Jun, 2025 from different towns in the seven Local Government Area that made up the Senatorial district. The participant Age range was among primary school pupils between 3 to 15years old. The representative towns were considered randomly to reflect even geographical spread.

3.4.1 Stool and Blood Sample Collection

The stool samples were collected in sterilized wide mouthed plastic containers and 3% formalin admixed to the faeces to preserve the sample and the parasite eggs. The samples were labelled with information about age, sex, and unique number before transported to the Laboratory for analysis.

3.5 Processing of faecal samples for geohelminths examination

The faecal examination was carried out using Roepstorff and Nansen (1998) method for flotation and sedimentation techniques. One gram of each faecal sample was collected and mixed with 4ml of 10% formol water in a test tube using an applicator stick. The mixture was sieved using a strainer into a beaker. The suspension was transferred into a test tube and 4ml ethyl acetate added. The whole mixture

was stirred and centrifuged for 1 minute at 3000 r.p.m. Plastic bulb pipette was used to loosen the layer of fatty faecal debris and was inverted to discard the supernatant. The sediment in the test tube was turned in upright position, and the sediment resuspended again. Plastic pipette was used to transfer a drop of the suspended sediment to a clean grease free slide which was covered with a clean cover slip and examined microscopically using x10 and x40 objective lens. The ova were identified using morphological features as described by Cheesbrough, (2012). The geohelminths were identified initially based on the morphology of the eggs. Subsequent confirmation of *A. lumbricoides* and speciation of hookworm was done using polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

3.6 Statistical Analysis

Data obtained were analyzed using SPSS (statistical package for social Science) Version 20.0. The data was analyzed and interpreted using analysis of variance (ANOVA), to determine the significant difference between the mean of various *geohelminth* parasites and *Salmonella spp* examined based on the geographical location of the water, blood and stool samples. The analysis was based on significance contamination level of P greater than or equal to 0.05% significance ($P \geq 0.05$).

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Prevalence of Geohelminths Parasites Identified Among Pupil in Various Local Government

The figure 4.1 below, revealed the overall prevalence of geohelminthiasis at percentage rate of 17.32% out 175 pupils who harboured at least one parasite species. (57.33%) of the students were infected with *Ascaris lumbricoides* 47(26.85%) recording higher in prevalence, followed by, *Strongyloides stercoralis* 37(21.14%), *Trichuris trichiura* 31(17.71%), *Ancylostoma canine* 32(18.28%) and *Ancylostoma duodenale* 28(16.00). In the pattern of infection occurrences as shown in table 4.1, light infection was recorded in *Ascaris lumbricoides* 36(20.77%), *Trichuris trichiura* 25(14.28%), *Strongyloides stercoralis* 19(10.85%), *Ancylostoma caninum* 12(6.85%) and *Ancylostoma duodenale* 15(8.57%). Moderate infections were recorded, *Ascaris lumbricoides* 7(4.00), *Trichuris trichiura* 1(0.57), *Strongyloides stercoralis* 10(5.71%), *Ancylostoma caninum* 20(11.42), and *Ancylostoma duodenale* 10(5.71%). While heavy infections intensity was recorded highest in *Strongyloides stercoralis* 8(4.57%), *Trichuris trichiura* 5(2.85%) followed by *Ascaris lumbricoides* 4(2.28%) while *Ancylostoma canine* and *Ancylostoma duodenale* recorded the least, (0%) and 3(1.71%) respectively. *A. lumbricoides* was the most prevalent species of STHs reported during the period under review while, hookworms had the lowest prevalence in agreement with global data. The high prevalence of *A. lumbricoides* observed by the present study may be attributable to high environmental contamination resulting from the large number of infected people, the durability of *Ascaris* eggs under varying environmental conditions, the high fecundity as well as the sticky nature of the shell of *Ascaris* egg which aids its attachment on human hands, fruits and vegetables.

Fig.4.1: Prevalence of geohelminth species

Table 4.1: Pattern of occurrence of Geohelminths infections among pupils in Anambra North

Infection intensity	Soil-transmitted helminths n (%)				
	<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	<i>Trichuris trichiura</i>	<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	<i>Ancylostoma caninum</i>	<i>Ancylostoma duodenale</i>
Light	36 (20.57)	25 (14.28)	19 (10.85)	12 (6.85)	15 (8.57)
Moderate	7 (4.00)	1 (0.57)	10 (5.71)	20(11.42)	10 (5.71)
Heavy	4 (2.28)	5 (2.85)	8 (4.57)	0	3(1.71)
Total	47 (26.85)	31 (17.71)	37(21.14)	32(18.28)	28 (16.00)

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study revealed the overall prevalence and pattern of occurrences of geohelminthiasis at percentage rate of 17.32% out 175 pupils who harboured at least one parasite species. *Ascaris lumbricoid* 47(26.86%) is the most prevalence, while *Ancylostoma duodenale* record the least prevalence rate 28(16.00%). *Strongyloids stercoralis* exhibited heavy infection intensity rate 8(4.57%), *Ascaris lumbricoides* showed light infection intensity rate 36(20.57%), while *Trichuris trichiura* showed moderate infection intensity of 1(0.57%). *A. lumbricoides* were the most prevalent species of STHs reported during the period under review while, hookworms had the lowest prevalence in agreement with global data. The high prevalence of *A. lumbricoides* observed by the present study may be attributable to high environmental contamination, the durability of *Ascaris* eggs under varying environmental conditions, the high fecundity as well as the sticky nature of the shell of *Ascaris* egg which aids its attachment on human hands, fruits and vegetables. This was in line with the study of Eniola *et al.*, (2019). Who recorded that a checklist of *Ascaris Lumbricoides*, hookworms, *Trichuris trichuria* and *Strongyloides Stercoralis* was generated from the pooled data of the four studied schools in which *A. Lumbricoides* occurred highest with 13% (26/200) while *S. Stercoralis* was the least prevalent at 2.50% (5/200). Among the schools sampled, St. James pilot Science primary schools' children were the most infected at 44% (22/50). Multiple infections were observed in three of the four schools sampled. Their findings showed no significant difference ($p>0.05$) in prevalence rates of different STHs infections in relation to age group and gender across schools. Which is in agreement with the work of Igbodika *et al.*, (2014), who stated that *Ascaris lumbricoides* was the most prevalent *helminth* parasite, 133 (26.60%) and *Entamoeba histolytica*, 105(21.0%). The high prevalence of infection could be attributed to the poor sanitary status and poor personal hygiene of the children.

DATA COLLECTION

Ethical Approval on data collection during the research was obtained from the Anambra State Ministry of Health

DECLARATION

The Author declared no conflict of interest

REFERENCES

- Ayinmode, A.B., and Fagbeni, B.O., (2010). Prevalence of Cryptosporidium Infection in Cattle from South Western Nigeria. *Veterinarski Arhive*, 80(6):723-731.
- Cheesbrough, M. (2012). District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries. *London: Cambridge University Press* 182-184.
- Igbodika, C.I., Anthony, O.E, and Emmy-Egbe, I.O. (2014). Prevalence of intestinal parasites among school children in rural community of Anambra State, Nigeria. *American Academic and Scholarly Research Journal*. Vol 6:4
- Nesheim, M.C. (1985). Nutritional aspects of *Ascaris suum* and *A. lumbricoides* infections. In Crompton DWT, Nesheim MC, Pawlowski ZS, editors. *Ascariasis and its public health significance*. London, Taylor & Francis. 147-160.
- Odiere, M.R., Opisa, S., Odhiambo, G., Jura, W.G., Ayisi, J.M, and Karanja, D.M. (2011). Geographical distribution of Schistosomissis and soil-transmitted helminthes among school children in informal settlements in kisumu City, Western Kenya. *Parasitology*. 138(12):1569-77.
- Onyenweife G. I. and Nwozor K. K. (2025). Innovations for SDG 6: Development of Novel Depth-to-Potable Groundwater Map of Anambra State, Southeast Nigeria, *International Journal of Innovative Environmental Studies Research* 13(1):107-124.